

Impact of Political News on Youth

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Abstract:- In this dissertation, people of 18 to 40 years of age have been established as youth and radio, electronic media, newspapers have been established as media. All the respondents in this research study are artists from Noida and watch/read/listen to news or regular consumers. This research, which was conducted with the help of offline Google Form, included 29 eminent women and 71 eminent male respondents. Among all the respondents included in the research, the highest number was in the age group of 18-25. Among the respondents included in this research, 72 percent watch/read/listen to news regularly and 28 percent irregularly. Most of the people involved in this research believe that news has an impact on them, they have changed their opinion, they discuss after listening/reading/watching the news. After analyzing the data obtained from this study, it was found that most of the voters who read/listen/watch political news are influenced by the news shown by the media. Most of the consumers involved in the research had knowledge of political current affairs. It is clear from the results obtained from this study that media not only increases people's knowledge but also provides them options and also exerts influence on them.

Keywords:- Political news, press, journalist, media, radio, television, cinema etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

Youth have an important role in any democratic country. Their role is increasing even more in a country like India, where the number of youth is the highest in the world. Youth in India decide the condition and direction of the country in every field. He has an important contribution in the field of politics. This is the group that decides which dynasty will take power and who will perform their duties in the nomination. If any movement gets the support of the youth, then that movement forces the governments to bow down, these youth also play a vital role in showing the way out to the governments. When media and youth talk in one voice about national interest and public welfare, the pace of development of the country increases. The synergy between media and youth is possible only when they work as complements to each other. In today's digital age, there is a great need for coordination between these two so that no anti-social element or miscreant can succeed in their intentions by spreading rumours. "Media is a complete system which includes mediums of information like printing press, journalists, electronic media, radio, cinema, internet etc." (Drishti). After legislature, legislature and judiciary, media is called the fourth pillar of democracy. "The first objective of a newspaper is to understand and express the wishes, views of the public. The second objective is to awaken desirable feelings among the public. The third is to

fearlessly reveal public faults – Mahatma Gandhi 1908 AD." (T.A. 2019 Page No. 46).

"News is the report of any recent event, idea or problem in which more and more people are interested and which has an impact on more and more people" (NCERT. 2022-23. Page No. 31). Newspapers have worked to create awareness in the society since the beginning. "In this era of information revolution, taking the help of media to influence the thoughts of the people and create public opinion is a natural process" (T.R. 2019, page no. 132). Media has been doing the work of educating the society since the beginning. "Media must hold governments and political parties accountable but public concerns should be at its centre and not institutions of power – M Venkaiah Naidu" (PIB 2019).

"Politics is a process of conflict resolution, through which efforts are made to coordinate competing interests" (Ku. No. 2019. Page No. 3). Politics is a policy made for the development of the state and country and the upliftment of the citizens, so that the country can achieve strategic development and establish a welfare state. "Etymologically, the adjective political begins with the Greek word 'Polis', which means city-state." (M.K.P. 2020 Page No. 11).

"If I have to decide whether we want a government without a newspaper or a newspaper without a government, I will not take even a moment to choose the second option" (T.A. 2019 p. no. 151). The impact of news on society is sometimes positive and sometimes negative. "Priming theory suggests that when most citizens make decisions about politics they are 'satisfied' and consider only what is recent or readily available" (C. L. 2008. Page no. 499). The discussions and debates taking place in the media may not change opinions but they definitely force one to think. "News coverage on political topics can mobilize citizens to vote in elections (and in some cases to abstain from voting) and in some cases news even influences vote choice" (C.L. 2008. Page No. 500.).

"Due to commercialization and market competition, in recent years the news media has tried to convert its niche market into a mass market. Due to the trend of selling entertainment in the name of news, today there is a lack of real and relevant information and information in the news" (NCERT. 2022-23. Page No. 44).

Youth play a major role in bringing social change in any country. "Governments have often failed in their duties because of the self-interests of most politicians and bureaucrats. But things can definitely turn positive if the youth have vision and play the role of a catalyst in the process of change which is inevitable – Jayaprakash Narayan" (The Hindu, 2015). The contribution of youth in social, political, cultural, economic and scientific changes is recorded in history. "In the words of Sir James, youth is a

bird which is spreading its wings with broken sticks and helplessness in the open sky of freedom and hope because youth can provide prosperity to its country through discovery and dreams” (D.B. 2018). “Swami Vivekananda ji considered the role of youth in nation building important, he believed that if the young generation uses its energy in the progress of the country, then the nation can be taken to a new level” (D.B. 2018). “Lok Satta founder Jayaprakash Narayan called upon the youth to play a meaningful role in nation-building and not get distracted. Despite various shortcomings, India is a great country, not because of the governments but because of the peace-loving people fighting against overwhelming odds” (The Hindu, 2015). “Abraham Lincoln was an advocate of democracy and equal rights for all. He had said that democracy is a system of governance made by the people, by the people and for the people (Drishti 2020). India is the mother of democracy, perhaps this is the reason why people living in every corner of India are sensitive towards politics. “Due to the growing competition for development and prosperity as well as destruction in the world, there is an equal decline in the development of life and human values. The basic foundation of Indian folk is ‘SarveBhavantuSukhinah and Satyameva Jayate’ (T.R. 2019, Page No. 130).

Around 600 BC Among the 16 Mahajanapadas of India, there were such districts as Vajji, Kuru etc. which were republican. “The Licchavi Republic of Vaishali is considered to be the world's first republic which was the capital of Vajji Sangha. It was formed in 500 BC. “(Drishti, 2018. P. No. 23). The movements taking place here also give birth to many big leaders, due to which all of them are successful in changing the condition and direction of the country. They rise and fall due to emotions and sympathy. “After Indira's assassination, not only was there an atmosphere of mourning in the entire country, but the entire country's sympathy was with Rajiv Gandhi. Rajiv Gandhi got the political benefit of this sympathy that Congress achieved success in the Lok Sabha elections, which even Jawaharlal Nehru and Indira Gandhi herself could not achieve” (Zee News, 2019).

Swedish radio talked about the scam in the purchase of Bofors, which was quickly picked up by the Indian media and loudly reported to the public. “On June 24, 1989, a cannon had united the entire opposition in the Lok Sabha. That too when there was no leader of the opposition. It was alleged that the company had bribed Rs 60 crore to Indian politicians and Defense Department officials for the deal, after which this news spread rapidly in the country's media. The Congress government of Rajiv Gandhi was expected to win the elections again, but the tables were turned” (AajTak, 2019). Congress had captured more than 400 seats in the last elections but could not get even half the seats in the 1989 general elections. After which V.P. Singh ji became the Prime Minister of India. The media worked to present alternatives other than Congress to the people of India. “The biggest weapon to end misgovernance is exposure. In the much-discussed 'Spy Catcher Case', it was said in an English court - 'The press has a legitimate role in exposing government scams. This should be the case in an open democratic society’ (T.A. 2019 p. no. 151).

“In the 21st century, media is playing an important role in parliamentary democracy. Changes with liberalization have led to a shift from public service to commercial enterprise. The growing economic interests of private media owners are affecting the credibility of the media” (Dezire, 2020). At one time, even the ethics of media were questioned when a major channel did live coverage of the 2008 terrorist attack. “The live coverage of the media helped the terrorists a lot as they were able to know about every action of the security forces on TV” (Amar Ujala, 2022).

It was the contribution of the media that many scams like 2G scam, coal scam, fodder scam etc. came to the fore in front of the public. National movement took place under the leadership of Anna Hazare. “Unlike political rallies, which see hired crowds, these meetings were attended mainly by the youth for whom Anna was a mix of Gandhi and a rock star. The Anna movement could be successful only because of the active role of the youth” (A.R. 2016. Page No. 184). The situation was such that the ongoing campaign against corruption changed the government.

“Media plays a huge role in the progress and development of any country. If it is said that media creates and reconstructs society, it would not be wrong.” (Dhyeya IAS).

“The dedication and sacrifice of the youth have made an incomparable contribution to all the important changes that have taken place in the world. Perhaps that is why it is said that “wherever youth move, youth move in that direction” (D.B. 2018). “To save our democracy it is necessary that youth enter politics. You have a great guide in Swami Vivekananda and if our youth come into politics with his inspiration, the country will be strong – Prime Minister Narendra Modi” (PIB 2021).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This entire study has been done keeping in mind the impact of political news on the youth. This entire research has been designed to know the role of media in the political process. W. R. According to Varg, “the literature of a field forms the foundation on which future work is built”. In the year 2020, SD Yogaraju found in his study that television and print media had an impact on political socialization and process and through mass media, the public is educated about their rights and duties for better participation in the political process. According to George Gerbner's Cultivation Theory, media influences the audience. According to this theory, it has a strong impact on heavy viewers, resulting in them suffering from mean world syndrome (an influx of thoughts that are beyond reality) (Wikipedia). Maxwell M Combs and Donald Shaw propounded ‘The Agenda Setting Theory’ in 1972. According to this, media has a powerful influence in the society in making people aware of the topics important to them. It is capable of telling people ‘What they should think about’ and then it is also capable of telling them ‘What they should think’ (S.A.K., K.A 2022. Page No. 50). According to research conducted by Jintu Gohain in the context of Assam, it was also found that issues driven by media are more influential on voting behaviour than old long-term factors. Campaigns conducted through media

leave a greater impression on people, and can reach more people in less time and using less resources. This medium is easy and effective for both the voter and the seeker. According to research conducted in Dharwad village of Karnataka, which is located in Hubli district, women who read newspapers are more interested in political information than women who use other media. B. S. Vijapur by A. S. In my study conducted under the guidance of Balasubramanya, I found that most of the youth receive political information through mass media.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Objective:

- To know whether political news has an impact on youth or not.
- To find out the most used news media for political news.
- To clarify the role of media in creating political awareness.
- To find out how political news helps youth in forming their political opinions.

B. Hypothesis:

- H1- Youth are influenced by the news shown (or published) by the media, they are influenced by it.
- H2- Youth decide their voting by watching/listening/reading political news.
- H3- Media helps in increasing the activism of youth in the field of politics.
- H4- Media plays an important role in bringing political awareness.

C. Field of Study:

This entire study will be done in Lucknow, the capital of Uttar Pradesh. Following are the reasons for choosing Lucknow as a research area:

- It is the capital of India's most populous state Uttar Pradesh.
- Since the headquarters of all the political parties of UP, Assembly, Secretariat and Chief Minister's residence are

in Lucknow, it also becomes the political center of Uttar Pradesh.

- Apart from Doordarshan and All India Radio, offices of many newspapers and news channels are also located here.

D. Sample:

The total population taken for the study is 100. The entire research process is survey based. This study has been completed using purposive sampling.

E. Young:

- Madhya Pradesh government organized Vedanta Youth Camp, in which people in the age group of 18 to 40 could register for free (JV 2023).
- Mukhyamantri Yuva Self-Employment Scheme, Uttar Pradesh, age for application - 18 to 40 (DIEP, U.P.)

Apart from the above, taking the previous study as the basis, in this study also people of 18 to 40 years of age have been considered as youth.

F. Research Design and Tools:

In the presented dissertation, mainly online questionnaire has been used as descriptive research design and study tool.

G. Technique of collecting facts:

- The primary source is the respondents filling out the online questionnaire.
- Newspapers, books, websites have been used as secondary sources.

H. Limitations of the study:

- Minimum resources
- Lack of time
- This study has been done in the context of Lucknow only. All the respondents included in this are voters of Lucknow.

I. Data Analysis:

A total of 100 respondents participated in this study. The details of the respondents included are as follows-

Part-1

Table 1: The details of the respondents

Sr. no.	Sex	respondents	Percentage
1.	Female	29	29
2.	Male	71	71
Total		100	100

From the observation of Table No. 1, it is clear that among the respondents included in the study, 29 percent of the respondents are female and 71 percent of the respondents are male. Therefore, most of the respondents are men.

Fig. 1: Age details of Respondents

From the analysis it is known that the number of respondents between 18 to 25 years of age is highest, whereas the number of respondents between 35 to 40 years of age is the least.

Fig. 2: Marital status details of respondents

It is clear from the above that the number of unmarried people is highest among the respondents included in the research.

Table 2: Educational status of respondents

Sr. no.	Qualification	respondents	percentage
1.	10th	1	1
2.	12th	5	5
3.	Graduation	53	53
4.	Post-graduation	38	38
5.	Other#	5	5
Total		100	100

#Other: PhD, Diploma etc.

It is clear from the above that the number of graduates is highest among the respondents included in the research.

Table 3: Details of respondents on the basis of religion

Sr. no.	Religion	Respondents	percentage
1.	Hindu	94	94
2.	Muslim	4	4
3.	Sikh	0	0
4.	Christian	0	0
5.	Other#	2	2
Total		100	100

#Other: Buddhist etc.

From the observation of Table No. 3, it is clear that 94 percent respondents are Hindu, 4 percent Muslim and 1 percent Buddhist respondents.

Table 4: Most used medium by respondents

Sr. no.	Medium	Respondents	percentage
1.	Newspaper	51	51
2.	Magazines	2	2
3.	Radio	1	1
4.	Television	46	46
Total		100	100

Analysis of Table No. 4 concludes that most of the respondents included in the study read newspapers. Whereas the number of people listening to radio is the lowest.

Fig. 3: Details of respondents who listen/watch/read news regularly or irregularly

From the above discussion it is concluded that the number of people reading/watching/listening to news regularly is highest.

Fig. 4: Details of time spent by respondents in watching/reading/listening to news

From the above discussion it is concluded that the people involved in the study spend less than an hour watching/reading/listening to the news.

Fig. 5: Details of Hindi newspapers most read by the respondents

From the observation of Fig. 5, it is known that out of the total respondents included in the study, 38 percent read Dainik Jagran, 31 percent Amar Ujala, 17 percent

Hindustan, 10 percent Navbharat Times, 4 percent Jansatta Hindi newspaper.

Fig. 6: Details of English newspapers most read by the respondents

Analysis of Fig. 6 concludes that most of the respondents included in the study read the times of India.

Fig. 7: Details of channels most watched by the respondents

From the discussion of the above, it is clear that the number of AAJ TAK viewers is the highest compared to other channels given in the above option.

Fig. 8: Details of magazines most read by the respondents

From the discussion of the above, it is clear that the number of India Today readers is the highest compared to other channels given in the above option.

Fig. 9: Description of impact of news on respondents

Analysis of Fig. 9 leads to the conclusion that most people are influenced by the news shown by the media.

Fig. 10: Description of respondents' opinions changes or not after watching/hearing/reading the news

By observing Fig. 10, it is clear that most of the people believe that they have changed their opinion after watching/reading/listening to the news.

Fig. 11: Description of respondents' liking or disliking after watching/hearing/reading the news

From the observation of Fig. 11, it is clear that out of the total respondents included in this study, 71 percent are those who have liked or disliked any leader after watching/hearing/reading any news.

Fig. 12: Details of respondents who discussed or did not discuss after watching/listening/reading the news

Observation of Fig. 12 shows that among the respondents included in this research, the number of people who discuss any news after watching/hearing/reading it is the highest.

Fig. 13: Description of topics that attracted respondents' attention

From the observation of Fig. 13, it is clear that news related to international affairs and political parties attracts the most people's attention.

Fig. 14: Description of respondents' reasons for watching/listening/reading political news

After observing Fig. 14, it is clear that among the respondents included in this study, most of the respondents read/watch/listen to the news for 'general knowledge'.

Fig. 15: Statement of opinion of the respondents on the role of media on the issue of corruption

From the observation of Fig. 15, it is clear that among the respondents included in this research, the number of people who believe that ‘media has an important role on the issue of corruption’ is highest among the respondents included in this study.

Fig. 16: Details of the opinions given by the respondents on the functioning of the ruling party

From the observation of Fig. 16, it is known that among the respondents included in this study, 57 percent of the respondents are satisfied with the functioning of the ruling party.

Fig. 17: Details of respondents' opinion on Parliament and Judiciary

From the observation of Fig. 17, it is clear that among the respondents included in this study, most of the respondents seemed satisfied with the functioning of the Parliament and the Judiciary. The number of people who consider the functioning of Parliament as satisfactory is less than those who consider the functioning of the Judiciary as satisfactory.

J. Part-3 Description of political knowledge of the respondents

Fig. 18: (age for voting)

Analysis of Fig. 18 shows that most of the respondents knew the minimum age for voting.

Fig. 19: (Age to become MLA in Assembly)

From the analysis of Fig. 19, it is clear that among the respondents included in this research, most of the people knew the minimum age required to become an MLA in the Legislative Assembly.

Fig. 20: (Governor of U.P.)

From the observation of Fig. 20, it is clear that 17 percent of the total respondents did not know the name of the Governor of Uttar Pradesh. Whereas 83 percent people knew the name of the UP Governor.

Fig. 21: (Leader of Opposition in UP Assembly)

From the observation of Fig. 21, it is clear that 83 percent of the total respondents knew the name of the Leader of Opposition of Uttar Pradesh Assembly. Whereas 17 percent people did not know the name of the leader of opposition of UP Assembly.

Fig. 22: (Chief Election Commissioner)

From the observation of Fig. 22, it is concluded that the name of the Chief Election Commissioner was known to most of the people. However, if we talk about the five questions, most of the respondents did not know the answer to this question as compared to other questions.

IV. RESULT

100 people took part in this study conducted with special reference to Lucknow, the capital of Uttar Pradesh. It is clear from Table No. 1 that 71 percent were male and 29 percent were female candidates. From the observation of Table No. 2, it is clear that among the men included in this study, 54.93 percent are graduates, 35.21 percent are masters, 1.41 percent are PhD and 2.82 percent have done some diploma or the other. Whereas 4.23 percent people have studied till 12th and 1.41 percent till 10th. From the analysis of Table No. 4, it is known that among the women included in this study, 48.28 percent women have obtained graduate degree and 44.83 percent women have obtained master's degree. Whereas 6.89 percent women have studied till 12th. From the detailed observation of Fig 3, it is clear that among the respondents participating in this survey,

68.97 percent women and 73.24 percent men are regular viewers/readers/listeners. Whereas 31.03 percent women and 26.76 percent men do not listen/read/watch news regularly.

From the detailed analysis of Fig. 10, it is concluded that among the male viewers/readers/listeners who watch/read/listen to the news regularly, 71.15 percent people believed that they change their opinion after watching the news, whereas 28.85 percent people Said that he has never changed his opinion. By observing Fig. 11, it is known that 75 percent of the men have liked or disliked a leader after being influenced by the news, whereas 25 percent of the men believe that they have never changed their decision due to the influence of the news. 76.92 percent of regular viewers/readers/listeners men discuss news after watching/reading/listening to it while 23.08 percent men do not discuss it at all. Among the regular male viewers/readers/listeners who watch/read/listen to news, 82.69 percent men believed that the news shown by the media has an impact on them while 17.31 percent people

believed that the news shown by the media has an impact on them. But there is no effect.

Among women who regularly watch/read/listen to news, 80 percent of the respondents admitted that they change their opinion after watching/read/listen to the news while 20 percent said that they never change their opinion. 75 percent women have either liked or not liked a leader under the influence of news, while 25 percent women believe that they have never changed their decision due to the influence of news. 85 percent of regular viewers/readers/listeners women discuss news after watching/reading/listening to it while 15 percent women do not discuss it at all. Among the regular female viewers/readers/listeners who watch/read/listen to news, 85 percent women believed that the news shown by the media has an impact on them while 15 percent women believed that the news shown by the media affects them. But there is no effect.

From the observation of Fig. 3 and Fig. 10, it is clear that among the female respondents who regularly watch/listen/read TV/Radio/newspaper, 66.67 percent admitted that after watching/listening/reading any news they have changed their opinion whereas 33.33 percent i.e. one third of the women have never changed their opinion. From the detailed analysis of Fig. 11, it is concluded that 55.56 percent women believed that after watching/hearing/reading any news, they liked any leader, while 44.44 percent women said that they were influenced by the news. Having never liked or disliked any leader. 88.89 percent women admitted that after watching/listening/reading the news, they have discussed a topic which they had not even talked about before, while 11.11 percent women have not discussed it. Among the irregular female viewers/readers/listeners who watch/read/listen to the news, 77.78 percent believe that the news shown by the media has an impact on them while 22.22 percent women believe that the news shown by the media has no impact on them. Has no effect.

Among the male respondents who regularly watch/listen/read TV/Radio/newspaper, 63.16 per cent admitted that they have changed their opinion after watching/listening/reading any news while 36.84 per cent of the male respondents have never changed their opinion. 63.16 percent men admitted that they have liked any leader after watching/hearing/reading any news, while 36.84 percent men said that they have never liked or disliked any leader due to influence of news. 63.16 percent of the respondents admitted that after watching/listening/reading the news, they have discussed a topic which they had not even talked about before, while 36.84 percent of the men have not discussed any. Among the irregular male viewers/readers/listeners who watch/read/listen to the news, 68.42 percent men believe that the news shown by the media has an impact on them while 31.58 percent men believe that the news shown by the media has an impact on them. There is no effect.

From the detailed analysis of Fig. 16 it is clear that among the male respondents who regularly watch/read/listen to the news, 15.38 percent do not have any opinion on the

functioning of the ruling party. While 23.08 percent people are highly satisfied, 42.31 percent are satisfied, 7.69 percent are highly dissatisfied and 11.54 percent regular male consumers are dissatisfied. Among the male respondents who watch/read/listen to news irregularly, 15.79 percent do not have any opinion on the functioning of the ruling party. While 5.26 percent people are highly satisfied, 68.42 percent are satisfied and 10.53 percent are highly dissatisfied, regular male consumers are dissatisfied.

Among women who watch/read/listen to news regularly, 50 percent do not have any opinion on the functioning of the ruling party. Whereas 5 percent are highly satisfied, 30 percent are satisfied, 5 percent are highly dissatisfied and 10 percent regular female consumers are dissatisfied. Among women who watch/read/listen to news irregularly, 77.78 percent do not have any opinion on the functioning of the ruling party. Whereas 22.22 percent irregular women consumers are satisfied with the functioning of Parliament. From Fig. 17,, it is known that among the male respondents who regularly watch/read/listen to the news, 19.23 percent do not have any opinion on the functioning of Parliament and 17.31 percent have no opinion on the functioning of the Judiciary. Whereas 26.92 percent of the Parliament and 23.08 percent of the people consider the functioning of the judiciary as highly satisfactory. 46.15 percent of the Parliament and 50 percent of the people consider the functioning of the judiciary as satisfactory. Among regular male consumers, the number of respondents who consider the functioning of Parliament and Judiciary as highly unsatisfactory is 3.85 percent and 1.92 percent respectively and the number of respondents who consider the functioning of Parliament and judiciary as unsatisfactory is 3.85 percent and 7.69 percent respectively.

Among the male respondents who watch/read/listen to news irregularly, 42.10 percent have no opinion on the functioning of Parliament and 31.58 percent have no opinion on the functioning of the Judiciary. Whereas 15.79 percent of the Parliament and 21.05 percent of the people consider the functioning of the judiciary as highly satisfactory. 26.32 percent of the Parliament and 36.84 percent of the people consider the functioning of the judiciary as satisfactory. Among the regular male consumers, no one considers the functioning of the Parliament as highly unsatisfactory while 5.26 percent people consider the functioning of the Judiciary as highly unsatisfactory. The number of respondents who consider the functioning of Parliament and Judiciary as unsatisfactory is 15.79 percent and 5.26 percent respectively.

Among women who watch/read/listen to news regularly, 35 percent do not have any opinion on the functioning of Parliament and 30 percent of the judiciary. Whereas 5 percent of Parliament and 10 percent of women consider the functioning of the judiciary as highly satisfactory. 50 percent of the Parliament and 60 percent of the women consider the functioning of the judiciary as satisfactory. Among the regular women consumers, no one considers the functioning of the judiciary as unsatisfactory, whereas 10 percent women consider the functioning of the Parliament as unsatisfactory.

Among women who watch/read/listen to news irregularly, 77.78 percent women do not have any opinion on the functioning of Parliament and the same number of women do not have any opinion on the functioning of Judiciary. Whereas 11.11 percent women consider the functioning of the Parliament as unsatisfactory and according to the data, no female viewer/listener/reader considers the functioning of the judiciary as unsatisfactory. Whereas 11.11 percent women consider the functioning of the Parliament and 22.22 percent women consider the functioning of the judiciary as satisfactory.

In the questionnaire of this study, some questions were asked to know political general knowledge. Among the women who watch/listen/read news regularly, 40 percent women were successful in answering all these questions, while 44.44 percent women who used news media irregularly were successful in answering all the questions. Whereas there was no woman who did not know the answer to even one of the questions asked. However, the name of the Chief Election Commissioner of India was known to 75 per cent of regular female viewers/readers/listeners and 66.67 per cent of irregular media users.

Talking about male respondents, only 34.62 percent men who are regular media users were able to answer all the questions while 36.84 percent men who use media irregularly were able to answer all these questions. There was no male reader/viewer/listener who read/watched/listened to the news irregularly or regularly who did not know the answer to even a single question. 47.37 percent irregular male viewers/readers/listeners and 63.46 percent regular consumers knew the name of the Chief Election Commissioner of India.

V. CONCLUSION

80 percent of the youth themselves admitted that the news shown by the media has an impact on them. 71 percent youth believe that after reading/hearing/watching political news, they have changed their opinion and liked or disliked a leader. Media influences youth. Looking at the data, it is clear that 71 percent people change their opinion on the basis of media news, whether they like or dislike a leader, it is clear that this will affect their voting also. 85 percent of the respondents have given their opinion on the role of media on the issue of corruption. 72 percent people have expressed some opinion on the functioning of the ruling party. 68 percent of the respondents have expressed some opinion towards the Parliament and 72 percent towards the judiciary. 55 percent people use media to increase their general knowledge. It is clear from these figures how media helps in increasing the political activism of youth. In Part 3, among the questions asked to know the political knowledge of the respondents, 37 percent of the candidates answered all the questions correctly. All these figures make clear the role of media in bringing awareness. In this study "Impact of political news on youth (with special reference to Lucknow)" it was found that media news has an impact on youth. Youth take the help of media in making their political decisions and also discuss these topics on the basis of their

news. These decisions taken by the youth also affect the politics of the country.

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